

Socket shield technique : A literature review article

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Abstract**Background:**

Dental implant therapy has become a well-established treatment modality for the replacement of missing teeth. In the esthetic zone, maintaining alveolar ridge contour and soft-tissue harmony following tooth extraction remains a clinical challenge. The socket shield technique (SST), a form of partial extraction therapy, aims to preserve the buccal root fragment to prevent alveolar bone resorption and support peri-implant tissues.

Objective:

This systematic review aimed to evaluate the clinical feasibility, success, and esthetic outcomes of the socket shield technique in immediate implant placement compared with conventional implant approaches.

Materials and Method:

Following PRISMA guidelines, an electronic search of PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect databases was conducted for English-language studies published between January 2000 and December 2018. Studies involving immediate implant placement using the SST with at least three months of follow-up were included. Data extraction focused on implant survival, osseointegration, shield-related complications, and esthetic outcomes. Study quality was assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal tools.

Results:

Twenty clinical studies met the inclusion criteria. Overall implant survival was high, with most studies reporting successful osseointegration and favorable esthetic results. Reported complications included shield exposure, migration, and infection, though these were infrequent and manageable. Minimal buccal bone loss and stable soft-tissue contours were consistent findings. The longest follow-up (up to five years) showed satisfactory long-term outcomes.

Discussion:

The SST demonstrated predictable maintenance of buccal bone and peri-implant soft tissues. However, the technique is operator-sensitive, with potential complications linked to shield handling and case selection. Most available evidence consists of case reports and small case series, with limited randomized controlled data.

Conclusion:

The socket shield technique appears to be a conservative and biologically sound approach for preserving alveolar ridge architecture and enhancing esthetic outcomes in immediate implant

placement. Despite encouraging results, further long-term randomized controlled trials are required to validate its predictability, standardize protocols, and confirm its long-term stability.

Keywords: *Socket shield technique, immediate implant placement, alveolar ridge preservation, partial extraction therapy, pink esthetics, dental implants*

Introduction: Dental implant therapy has become one of the most widely accepted treatment options for the replacement of missing teeth because of its predictable and successful clinical outcomes. Following implant placement, attention must be directed not only toward achieving osseointegration but also toward maintaining esthetic harmony, especially in the anterior maxillary region. Implant placement after tooth extraction often leads to alterations in the contour of both hard and soft tissues surrounding the extraction and pontic areas^{1,2,3}. Among these, the buccal aspect is more prone to alveolar ridge resorption than the lingual aspect; therefore, maintaining adequate alveolar bone support is essential for achieving a natural and esthetically pleasing soft-tissue contour^{3,4}. To recreate a natural emergence profile of the prosthesis, adequate dimensions of hard and soft tissues are required, which can be accomplished through socket preservation or alveolar ridge preservation procedures.

Alveolar ridge preservation, first introduced in the mid-1980s, is a technique designed to maintain ridge volume by placing grafting material within the extraction socket, with or without the addition of a barrier membrane or soft-tissue coverage. This procedure gained popularity due to its conceptual simplicity and clinical reliability and has since been extensively evaluated in the literature^{5,6}. Ridge preservation can be performed using soft-tissue grafts, hard-tissue grafts, or a combination of both⁵. In addition, various biomaterials have been employed for grafting purposes, including autogenous, allogeneic, xenogeneic, and alloplastic bone substitutes, as well as adjunctive materials such as platelet-rich plasma, platelet-rich fibrin, bone morphogenetic proteins, Emdogain, and cell-based therapies^{6,7}.

The outcome of ridge preservation depends on the materials and techniques employed. Guided bone regeneration utilizes barrier membranes to facilitate selective bone growth and enhance soft-tissue esthetics for optimal prosthetic outcomes. In connective tissue grafting, autogenous connective tissue serves as the grafting material. Techniques that retain a portion of the tooth root—collectively termed *partial extraction therapies*—include the socket shield and pontic shield techniques. The current review focuses on the socket shield technique as a key modality within this therapeutic concept.

The root submergence technique, developed to preserve both alveolar bone and soft-tissue architecture, has recently regained attention in prosthetic implant therapy, particularly in the esthetically sensitive anterior maxillary zone. Initially described in 1953, this approach evolved into the socket shield technique, introduced in 2007, which allowed immediate implant placement within a retained root fragment. In 2015, it was further combined with socket grafting to maintain ridge contour at pontic sites⁸ Hürzeler et al. first detailed the socket shield

concept in 2010, and Ghapure et al. later provided the first systematic review in 2017. Since then, new studies have emerged, necessitating an updated systematic analysis of its clinical efficacy.

Partial extraction therapy seeks to minimize alveolar bone resorption following tooth extraction by preserving the buccal portion of the tooth root, thereby preventing buccal cortical collapse⁸. When performed in conjunction with immediate implant placement, the socket shield technique can preserve natural soft-tissue contours while being minimally invasive—eliminating the need for flap elevation, second-stage surgery, periosteal-releasing incisions, or additional bone grafting materials^{9,10}. Several authors have proposed technical modifications to enhance the predictability and esthetic outcome of this method^{1,2,11}

Despite its advantages, certain complications have been reported in clinical cases, including infection, shield exposure, or fragment migration, which in some instances led to implant failure; however, such complications are rarely attributed to the technique itself¹¹. Some failures have been linked to shield mobility or displacement during or after implant placement¹². Conversely, other studies have reported reduced complication rates when preoperative 3D imaging or CBCT was used for precise planning. Buccal bone resorption can be effectively avoided by retaining a thin (approximately 1 mm) crescent-shaped root fragment on the buccal side. Although this approach is less invasive, it demands a high level of surgical expertise¹². To date, there remains no clear consensus on the long-term stability or esthetic predictability of the socket shield technique.¹³

Therefore, the present systematic review aimed to comprehensively analyze the available literature to assess the clinical feasibility and success of the socket shield technique. The primary objective was to determine whether this approach ensures long-term stability in implant-supported restorations, while the secondary objective was to evaluate its effectiveness in enhancing esthetic outcomes in anterior fixed prosthetic treatments.

Materials and methods:

This review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. To prepare and structure this review, the focused question was elaborated using the population, intervention, comparison, and outcome (PICO) format as detailed below: Population—subjects with immediate implant placement in the maxilla or mandible using the socket shield technique with follow-up after implant placement; Intervention—dental implant therapy using the socket shield technique; Comparison—other implant placement methods not using the socket shield technique; Outcome—survival of the implant and adverse effects of the socket shield technique. The focused question (PICO) was: Is there a difference in implant survival, esthetic result, and complications between immediate implant placement using the socket shield technique and immediate implant placement without using this technique? An electronic search was

performed to identify relevant studies in PubMed-Medline, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect for studies published in English from January 2000 to December 2018, in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. The search terms were “root submergence technique,” “socket shield technique,” “dental implant,” and “immediate implant” in various combinations, and reference lists of similar or recommended articles were also manually searched. Studies were included if they met the following criteria:(1)case report, case control, cohort study, retrospective case series, or randomized controlled trial; (2) use of the socket shield principle; and (3) implant immediately placed after tooth extraction. Exclusion criteria were: (1) follow-up of less than 3 months after implant placement and (2) animal experiments. Two of the review authors assessed the title, abstract, and full-text availability of all studies identified in the electronic search, and articles were included based on the title and abstract and the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All articles were independently assessed for relevance, eligibility, data extraction, quality assessment, and risk of bias. For clinical studies, the outcomes assessed were implant osseointegration, shield exposure, shield mobility, shield infection, shield migration, and soft tissue contour, while the radiologic outcome was buccal/crestal bone loss. The included studies were analyzed for complications and adverse effects reported by their respective authors, and data tables, radiographs, and clinical images presented in these studies were also analyzed to identify overlooked or missed complications. Predefined data collection spreadsheets were used for the assessment of each article, and collected data included the author’s names, publication year, sample size, time and area of implant placement, loading protocol, complications and adverse effects, and follow-up duration. Evaluations were carried out independently by two reviewers (OT and SR) and confirmed by consensus. The quality of each included study was assessed by two independent evaluators (OT and SR), and any potential disagreements were resolved by consensus. The included studies were evaluated using the “Checklist for Case Reports, Case Series, Cohort Studies and Randomized Controlled Trials, in the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal tools”. To assess the quality of the studies, the included studies were rated using the checklist for each article type and classified as good (total score more than 66.7%), moderate (total score 33.4–66.6%), and poor (total score less than 33.3%). The heterogeneity of the data was assessed to determine whether a meta-analysis could be performed, and the level of agreement between the reviewers regarding relevant factors in the studies was determined using kappa statistics. Data were analyzed using SPSS software (SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23.0; IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).

Results : Hürzeler et al. (2010) first described the socket shield technique by placing an immediate implant in the mandibular premolar region, reporting no complications after six months of follow-up. Kan et al. (2013) performed the technique in the maxillary right central incisor with immediate loading and observed successful outcomes after twelve months. Similarly, Al-Dary (2013) conducted the procedure on a single-rooted maxillary tooth with immediate loading and found no adverse effects over a five-month period. Siormpas et al.

(2014) evaluated 46 immediately placed implants in the maxillary anterior region and noted only one case of apical root resorption after a follow-up of 24 to 60 months. Troiano et al. (2014) studied ten implants placed immediately in the anterior regions of both jaws, loaded after three months, with no complications and satisfactory results at six months.

Bäumer et al. (2015) reported a single mandibular case where the implant was loaded after six months, showing a mean labial bone loss of 0.88 mm, which was within acceptable limits. Gluckman et al. (2015) evaluated a single immediate implant in the maxillary central incisor region and found no complications after a 12-month follow-up. Al-Dary (2015) also reported a successful outcome for a maxillary premolar implant loaded after four months, with no adverse findings. In another study, Bäumer et al. (2017) placed ten implants in the maxillary first premolar region with delayed loading after five months, observing minimal buccal tissue loss and minor mid-facial recession after an average follow-up of 58 months. Roe et al. (2017) performed an immediate implant placement in the maxillary central incisor and achieved favorable results without complications after two years.

Barakat et al. (2017) evaluated ten immediately placed implants in single-rooted maxillary teeth, loaded after four months, and recorded minimal bone loss and probing depth changes at seven months. Aslan et al. (2018) placed one immediate implant in the maxillary right central incisor with no adverse effects at twelve months. Gluckman et al. (2018) conducted a large-scale retrospective study involving 128 implants placed immediately in the maxillary and mandibular anterior and premolar regions. They reported a few cases of implant osseointegration failure, socket shield exposure, and migration, with an overall positive outcome over one to four years.

Pardo et al. (2018) inserted a single immediate implant in the maxillary lateral incisor region, loaded after three months, and observed no complications after six months. Hinze et al. (2018) analyzed seventeen immediately placed implants in the anterior and premolar regions and found minimal soft tissue contour changes and stable gingival margins after three months. Han et al. (2018) placed forty immediate implants in both maxillary and mandibular anterior regions and reported uneventful healing and good esthetic results after twelve months. Dohièm et al. (2018) evaluated a single immediate implant in the maxillary canine region with delayed loading after four months and found no complications over a two-year follow-up.

Walid (2018) performed a similar case with an immediate implant in the maxillary first premolar, loaded after six months, and noted minimal volumetric bone loss and stable ridge contour at six months. Guo et al. (2018) observed excellent outcomes with a single maxillary central incisor implant placed immediately and loaded after six months, with no reported complications over a 24-month follow-up. Lastly, Mattar (2018) evaluated an immediate implant in the maxillary lateral incisor region with delayed loading after six months and reported uneventful healing and favorable results after two years.

Discussion: Implant placement within the esthetic zone presents significant challenges, as the results depend on several factors such as the timing of placement, the alveolar socket topography, dimensions of soft and hard tissues, the clinician's expertise, implant design and positioning, and even patient-related factors¹⁴. Hence, to minimize the failure rate of the socket shield technique, it is crucial to understand its indications and contraindications to identify suitable roots for the procedure. The technique is indicated in cases involving vertical root fractures, non-restorable teeth, teeth requiring extraction with immediate implant placement, and ridge preservation to prevent buccopalatal collapse and maintain papillary and soft tissue contours around the implant. Conversely, it is contraindicated in the presence of residual roots with pulp or apical pathology, periodontal disease, or traumatic occlusion⁸.

Most of the reviewed studies demonstrated that the socket shield technique yielded favourable esthetic outcomes, with the longest reported follow-up of approximately five years showing highly satisfactory results¹⁵. Among the 20 studies reviewed, only one documented complications or adverse outcomes related to the technique¹¹. In that study, when an implant failed to osseointegrate, clinicians examined the integrity of the socket shield. If it remained intact, the implant was replaced; if not, the shield was removed before implant replacement. Of five failed osseointegration cases, two maintained intact shields, while three required shield removal. Additionally, three cases developed infections necessitating shield removal and implant replacement, an approach consistent with another study. To prevent infection, clinicians must ensure complete removal of root remnants after extraction²⁴. Maintaining a contamination-free field and preserving the periodontal tissues during healing are also essential to achieve proper osseointegration.

Among 12 cases of internal shield exposure, eight required only observation, while in four, the exposed root portion was reduced using a diamond bur. In four cases of external shield exposure, coronal trimming of the shields was performed to promote soft tissue closure, with two cases requiring additional connective tissue grafts to enhance healing. Preventing sharp edges on the shield is critical, as these may contribute to soft tissue exposure¹⁶. In cases of shield migration, implants were restored without further reduction of the shield. Mattar discussed the potential for shield migration, its causes, and management strategies.¹⁶

The key outcome parameters for the socket shield technique include implant survival, biological complications, and prosthetic complications, which can be assessed through clinical evaluation and radiographic imaging, such as CBCT¹⁷. Implant survival is defined as the implant being functional and present one year after placement¹⁷. However, nine of the twenty reviewed studies had a follow-up of less than one year, highlighting the need for further research with longer observation periods, as one study reported bone loss occurring over ten years after implantation using this technique. Documented biological and prosthetic complications include postoperative discomfort or swelling, shield or implant mobility, peri-implantitis, marginal bone loss, and shield resorption¹⁷.

It remains challenging to definitively state that the socket shield technique enhances esthetic results since most existing studies are case reports or case series lacking control groups. However, one high-quality randomized controlled trial included a control group and concluded that the socket shield technique appears to be a safe and effective approach for alveolar bone preservation, significantly reducing both horizontal and vertical bone loss compared with conventional implant placement. Consequently, the socket shield technique can be considered a minimally invasive procedure that offers favorable esthetic outcomes^{18,19,20}.

Conclusion: The socket shield technique represents a biologically driven, conservative approach to preserve the buccal bone plate and peri-implant soft-tissue architecture in immediate implant placement scenarios, particularly in the aesthetic zone. The current literature suggests favourable implant survival rates, reduced bone remodelling (especially buccal plate) and improved soft-tissue outcomes compared with conventional protocols. However, these findings come with caveats: the evidence base remains limited (few RCTs, variable follow-up, technique heterogeneity), the technique is sensitive and demands high surgical proficiency, and long-term outcomes (both hard and soft tissues, and shield fragment behaviour) are still not well established.

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